

SHORT NOTES

The Role of CO_2^- Radical in the Induced Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Organic Acids

K. Kumar and L. K. Saxena

The reduction of mercuric chloride by organic acids under the inductive influence of oxidising agents, such as KMnO_4 , potassium peroxydisulphate etc., has been explained in two ways. One mechanism pertains to the formation of formic acid as an intermediate necessity¹⁻³ and the other on the free radical CO_2^- ($\text{Hg}^{2+} + \text{CO}_2^- \longrightarrow \text{Hg}^+ + \text{CO}_2$)⁴⁻¹¹

This communication deals with a mechanism which accounts for the various characteristics of the reaction and simultaneously explains also the positive tests obtained for formic acid as an intermediate transient⁴⁻⁵.

Many organic acids (e.g. oxalic, malonic, tartaric etc.) alone are not able to reduce mercuric chloride even at high temperature but in presence of potassium peroxydisulphate or potassium permanganate they do so after an initial period of induction.¹ This clearly suggests that as a result of the interaction of the organic acid and the inductor, some active product is produced which reduces Hg^{2+} to the Hg^+ state. The nature of this active product is the most fundamental problem for arriving at a tentative mechanism.

Taking the case of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ as the reducing ion and MnO_4^- or $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ as the inducing ion, the mechanisms for the $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} - \text{MnO}_4^-$ and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} - \text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ systems are as follows:

(I) $\text{KMnO}_4 - \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ system: (Formation of Manganic complex):

(II) $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 - \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ system :

*activated

1. Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1917, 111, 690; *this Journal*, 1928, 5, 203; *Proc Acad. Amsterdam.*, 1920, 23, 308.
2. Bauer, *Z. Phys Chem.* 1908, 69, 683.
3. MacMohan *et al.* *This Journal*, 1943, 20, 142, 307.
4. Ghosh *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1950, 19, 174.
5. Waters *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217.
6. Cartledge, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 906.
7. Weiss, *Disc.*, 1947, 21, 188.
8. Ladbury and Cullis, *Chem. Rev.*, 1958, 403.
9. Waters *et al.*, *Quat. Rep.*, 1959.
10. Saxena and Singhal, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 405; 1961, 38, 863.
11. Mathur and Bansal, *ibid.*, 1965, 42, 232, 235.

In both the above mechanisms, the initial period of induction has been described as the time required for the generation of the free radical CO_2^- , which is the active substance referred to above and is produced as a result of the interaction of the oxidising agent and the acid. The free radical CO_2^- has also been formulated with other organic acids⁶⁻¹¹ in the reaction between mercuric chloride and organic acids induced by potassium permanganate or potassium peroxydisulphate. The role of this free radical is regarded as a chain carrier and has been supposed to control the mechanism of the process of the reduction of Hg^{2+} to the Hg^+ state by the following reaction:

The reducing property of CO_2^- is supported by the fact that CO_2 in presence of a reducing agent exerts a catalysing influence on the reduction of mercuric chloride¹⁰ probably due to formation of CO_2^- as a result of interaction of CO_2 and an electron in presence of a reducing agent:

Formation of formic acid as an intermediate product, as detected by spot test, can be explained by the following mechanism similar to that suggested by Jordan and Smith¹⁰,

The transient intermediate radical HCO_2 is analogous to the free radical HO_2 (as suggested by Weiss⁷) both being formed by identical one-electron and one-proton transfer sequences.

Even if it be admitted that this transient formic acid is responsible for the reduction of mercuric chloride, as is the view of certain workers, the fact remains that it is the CO_2^-

FIG. 1

radical which is responsible for the formation of formic acid and as such its role can hardly be ignored. The problem that now confronts is to investigate whether CO_2^- radical is more effective in bringing about the reduction of Hg^{++} ion by the reaction path (A) or first converting itself to formic acid by the reaction path (B) and then reducing it.

Our observations show that the amount of reduction of mercuric chloride by 0.2N oxalic acid in presence of an inductor ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$) is far greater than that by 0.2N formic acid alone or in presence of the same inductor under similar conditions (Fig. 1, curves 2, 3 and 4). Similar observations were obtained with other organic acids and inductor potassium permanganate. This is suggestive of the fact that had formic acid (formed as an intermediate product) been totally responsible for the reduction of mercuric chloride in the case of oxalic acid-inductor system, the amount of reduction could not have exceeded that in the case of formic acid alone or in presence of inductor (Fig. 1, curves 2, 3 and 4).

That formic acid is less effective in reducing mercuric chloride suggests that the over-all reaction follows the (A) path, which may be possibly due to CO_2^- radical having a greater affinity for the Hg^{++} ion than for a proton. It is probable that only a very small fraction of the CO_2^- radicals produced may react with H^+ ions yielding formic acid. When the H^+ -ion concentration of the reaction mixture is increased, the CO_2^- radicals combine with the excessive H^+ ions to form formic acid by path (B), thereby resulting in less reduction. This is supported by the observations of Saxena and Singhal¹⁰ and Mathur and Bansal¹¹.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. C. P. Singhal and Dr. O. P. Bansal, for taking keen interest in the work and to Dr. S. N. Srivastava, Head of the Chemistry Department for providing necessary facilities. They are thankful to the U.G.C. for awarding a fellowship to one of them (K. Kumar).

